

Chelate Formation between Trivalent Aluminium and *p*-Hydroxy Phenacylidene-*p*-Dimethyl Amino Aniline. Studies on the Composition and Stability of the Chelate

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The formation of a violet coloured chelate between aluminium (III) and *p*-hydroxy phenacylidene *p*-dimethylamino aniline with maximum absorption at 535 m μ has been studied at 28°. The composition of the chelate and the apparent stability constant were found to be 1 : 2 (M : L) and 0.3919×10^9 respectively. The composition and structure of the chelate formed were also confirmed by chemical analysis and I.R. spectral studies respectively. The free energy change of formation has also been calculated.

Kröhnke and Gröss¹ were the first to report that *p*-dimethyl amino anil of phenyl glyoxal could interact with different Lewis acids causing a bathochromic effect in the molecule, and thus, offering a possibility of chelate formation. A survey of literature reveals that chelating characteristics of such anils obtained from different keto aldehydes and aromatic amino compounds have not been studied in detail. *p*-Hydroxy phenacylidene *p*-dimethyl amino aniline was found to be an excellent chromogenic reagent for various inorganic cations in non-aqueous medium with large absorbance in the visible range of the spectrum. It was, therefore, thought worthwhile to study the molecular composition, stability and the other thermodynamic properties of the chelate formed between Al⁺³ and the above reagent.

EXPERIMENTAL

Synthesis of p-hydroxy phenacylidene p-dimethyl amino aniline: *p*-Hydroxy phenyl glyoxal was prepared by the oxidation of *p*-hydroxy acetophenone with selenium dioxide². Alcoholic solutions of equimolecular quantities of *p*-hydroxy phenyl glyoxal and *p*-dimethyl amino aniline were refluxed over a water bath for about an hour. On cooling the resulting mixture, a solid shining, lustrous solid was obtained. The anil was dried and crystallised from hot alcohol m.p. 92°.

Reagent and apparatus: Stock solutions of anhydrous aluminium chloride and that of the reagent were prepared in methanol free acetone. The metal content was estimated gravimetrically as Al₂O₃. Bausch and Lomb 'Spectronic—20' was used for taking all spectrophotometric measurements in the visible region. I.R. spectra were recorded in solid state by KBr-technique, employing Perkin-Elmer Infra-cord. Absorbance investigations were carried out at 28°.

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1. F. Kröhnke and K. F. Gröss, *Chem. Ber.*, 1956, **92**, 36.

2. G. Fodor and O. Konaes, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 1045.

DISCUSSION

Nature of the complex formed : The method of Vosburg and Cooper³ was employed to determine the nature of the complex formed in the solution. The absorbance values of mixtures in various ratios of the reactants show that only one complex was formed with λ max 535 m μ . The λ max of the ligand was at 425 m μ .

Effect of temperature : Samples were heated on an electrical water bath fitted with a water-condenser, cooled to room temperature and the absorbance was measured after making up the volume. There was no difference in the absorbance of this sample and that prepared at room temperature. The complex was, thus, stable over a wide range of temperature variations.

Stability of colour at room temperature : The colour of the chelate did not depend on reaction time and assumed its full intensity instantaneously and retained even after 24 hours, showing the stability of the chelate.

Composition of the chelate : The ratio of aluminium (III) to the ligand was determined by Job's continued variation⁴, slope ratio⁵ and mole-ratio⁶ methods. All the three methods showed the chelate to have 1 : 2 ratio of Al(III) to the organic ligand (vide Figs. I, II and III respectively.)

Isolation and analysis of the compound : The chelate was isolated by mixing equimolar solutions of the metal ion and that of the ligand in the ratio 1 : 2, and was, then, concentrated in a vacuum oven. The solid mass, thus obtained, was washed with petroleum ether (60°-80°)

3. W. C. Vosburg and G. R. Cooper, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, **64**, 1630.
4. P. Job, *Compt. rend.*, 1925, **180**, 928; *Ann. Chim.*, 1928, **9**, 113.
5. A. E. Harvey and D. L. Manning, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4488.
6. J. H. Yoe and A. L. Jones, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1944, **16**, 11.

to remove the greasy adhering mass and then crystallised with acetonitrile to obtain shining violet compound. The resulting chelate was hygroscopic in nature, so necessary precautions were taken not to expose it.

FIG III

The organic matter of 0.2 to 0.5 gm. of the chelate was decomposed by nitric acid. The residue was cooled and triturated by glass distilled water. The results of the chemical analysis were as follows :

Found : Al, 4.08%; C, 57.29%; H, 4.79%; N, 8.30%.

Calc. Al, 4.03%; C, 57.35%; H, 4.72%; N, 8.36%.

Evaluation of stability constant : The apparent stability constant of the chelate formed was calculated from the absorbance data by the mole -ratio method.

Considering the dissociation of the chelate—

C O O (Initial concn.)

C(1- α) C α 2 α C (Final concn.)

where, C = Concentration of the complex in moles/litre.

α = Degree of dissociation.

$$\alpha = \frac{E_m - E_s}{E_s}$$

where E_s and E_m have their usual significance.

$$\text{Stability constant} \quad K = \frac{C(1-\alpha)}{\alpha C(2\alpha C)^2}$$

$$= \frac{1-\alpha}{4\alpha^3 C^2}$$

The value of K, stability constant, was found to be 0.3919×10^9 at 28° .

The value of charge in free energy (ΔF) on complex formation has also been determined at 28°. The expression⁷, $\Delta F = -RT \ln K$ relating to the stability constant K to the free energy change of reaction was employed for evaluating the value ΔF , which was found to be $-15.42K$ cal/mole.

*I. R. spectral studies*⁸: The seats of interaction of the ligand with the metal ion could be confirmed by studying the infra-red spectra of the ligand and of the complex. In the ligand the stretching frequency of an aroyl ketone was found around 1700 cm^{-1} , while that of the azomethine grouping at 1600 cm^{-1} . On chelation these two frequencies were shifted to 1650 cm^{-1} and 1525 cm^{-1} respectively, confirming the two positions to offer location for binding with the metal to cause chelation.

Structure of the chelate: The following tentative structure may be assigned to the chelate on the basis of the above observations.

The existence of chlorine ion outside the coordination sphere could be explained on the basis that the addition of alcoholic silver nitrate solution to the complex solution resulted in the formation of a white precipitate soluble in ammonia.

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8. C. N. R. Rao, 'Chemical applications of Infra-red spectroscopy', Academic Press, 1963.